

A Study On Consumer Buying Behaviour Towards Flipkart Mobile Application

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Abstract- The rapid growth of e-commerce and smartphone usage has significantly transformed consumer buying behaviour. Online shopping platforms provide convenience, variety, and easy access to products, influencing consumer decisions. This study aims to analyse the buying behaviour of consumers towards the Flipkart mobile application. Primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire from 100 respondents. The findings reveal that factors such as discounts, product variety, user-friendly interface, and delivery services play a major role in influencing consumer decisions. The study concludes that Flipkart is widely preferred due to its convenience and attractive offers, but improvements in delivery speed and product quality can further enhance customer satisfaction.

Keywords- Consumer buying behaviour, Flipkart, e-commerce, customer satisfaction, offers, delivery, online payment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Consumer buying behaviour refers to the process by which individuals select, purchase, and use products to satisfy their needs. In recent years, online shopping has become more popular due to technological advancements and increased internet usage.

The Flipkart mobile application has emerged as one of the leading online shopping platforms in India. It provides various features such as product comparison, secure payment options, customer reviews, and fast delivery services. These features influence consumer buying decisions and enhance the overall shopping experience.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- Hoffman et al. (1999) stated that security and privacy are key factors influencing online consumer trust.
- Jarvenpaa et al. (2000) found that website security increases customer confidence in online shopping.
- Sharma (2018) concluded that mobile app usability significantly affects consumer buying behaviour.
- Gupta & Verma (2017) highlighted that secure payment systems reduce perceived risk among consumers.

III. OBJECTIVES

- To study consumer buying behaviour towards the Flipkart mobile application.
- To identify factors influencing online purchase decisions.
- To analyse customer satisfaction levels.
- To provide suggestions for improving online shopping experience.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used convenience sampling to select 100 respondents who use the Flipkart mobile application. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire based on respondents' availability and willingness to participate.

Sample Size

The sample size of the study consists of 100 respondents who are users of the Flipkart mobile application.

V. DATA COLLECTION

Data were collected from both primary and secondary sources.

Primary Data:

Collected from 100 respondents using a structured questionnaire who use the Flipkart mobile application.

Secondary Data:

Collected from books, journals, websites, and previous studies related to consumer buying behaviour and Flipkart.

VI. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Product Mostly Bought On Flipkart Of The Respondents

S.N O	PARTICULARS	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENT AGE
1	ELECTRONIC	20	20.4
2	FASHION	33	33.7
3	HOME APPLIANCES	22	22.4
4	GROCERIES	8	8.2
5	OTHER	15	15.3
	TOTAL	100	100

SOURCE: PRIMARY DATA INTERPRETATION:

Table 4.11 displays the products mostly bought by the respondents on Flipkart. It shows that 20.4% of the respondents mostly buy electronic products, 33.7% of the respondents buy fashion products, 22.4% of the respondents buy home appliances, 8.2% of the respondents buy groceries, and 15.3% of the respondents buy other products. Thus, among 100% of the respondents, the majority 33.7% of the respondents mostly buy fashion products on Flipkart.

PRODUCT MOSTLY BOUGHT ON FLIPKART OF THE RESPONDENTS

FLIPKART VALUE FOR MONEY OF THE RESPONDENTS

S.No	Particulars	No.Of Respondents	Weighted Average	Rank
1	Strongly Agree	39	156	I

2	Agree	36	108	Ii
3	Neutral	18	36	Ii
4	Disagree	5	5	Iv
	Total	100	305	

SOURCE: PRIMARY DATA INTERPRETATION:

Table 4.22 displays the respondents' opinion regarding whether flash sales increase their buying behaviour, analysed using a weighted average and ranking method. It shows that 39% of the respondents strongly agree (weighted score 156, rank I), 36% agree (weighted score 108, rank II), 18% are neutral (weighted score 36, rank III), and 5% disagree (weighted score 5, rank IV).

Thus, based on the weighted ranking, the majority of the respondents (39%) strongly agree that flash sales increase their buying behaviour, which holds the first rank among all responses.

FLIPKART VALUE FOR MONEY OF THE RESPONDENTS

FINDING

- The majority of the respondents mostly buy fashion products on Flipkart at 33.7 percent.
- The majority of the respondents strongly agree that Flipkart provides value for money at 39 percent.

Suggestions

- Improve delivery speed and logistics.
- Ensure better product quality control.
- Enhance customer support services.
- Strengthen cybersecurity measures.
- Encourage genuine customer reviews.

IX. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that the Flipkart mobile application plays a vital role in shaping consumer buying behaviour. Convenience, product variety, and attractive offers are the key

factors influencing customers. Although users are generally satisfied, improvements in delivery and product quality can further enhance the shopping experience. Understanding consumer behaviour helps companies develop better strategies and improve customer satisfaction.

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